

Supplementary Materials for

**Kilometric sea-level changes during the Messinian salinity crisis caused by
river erosion and climate**

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This PDF file includes:

Figs. S1 and S2

Other Supplementary Materials for this manuscript include the following:

Movie S1.

Movie S2.

Movie S3.

Fig. S1.

Sensitivity of lake elevation evolution to the lithospheric elastic thickness. Results for a T_e of 10 km (M4, blue) compared to the reference model M0 ($T_e=20$ km). Legend as in Fig. 2. Smaller T_e values predict deeper lake systems in the Mediterranean. The persistence of the drawdown cycles during the MSC was favored by the low T_e values imposed by the Neogene tectonics in the Mediterranean. The value adopted for the reference model (20 km) is a compromise between the lower values obtained in Neogene basins and the much older remnants of the Tethyan lithosphere in the E Mediterranean. The phenomenon described in this paper is not substantially modified by the value adopted for T_e .

Fig. S2. Sensitivity of lake elevation evolution to precipitation. A) Precipitation and evaporation (blue) and the evolution of the sediment volume accumulated in the Mediterranean (red line), for model M5 (10% less precipitation P) and for the reference model M0 (grey dashed lines). B) Evolution of lake elevation for M0 (grey) and M5 (blue). Other legend as in Fig. 2. Lower precipitation leads to more sedimentation because it increases the seafloor exposed to subaerial erosion by making the lakes deeper and shallower. More importantly, lower precipitation leads to the water level to barely reach levels above -200 m.

Movie S1.

Evolution of model M0 (reference model). Legend as in Figs. 1 and 2.
Available at [\[YouTube link to be updated\]](#)

Movie S2.

Evolution of model M1 (less erosion). Legend as in Figs. 1 and 2.
Available at [\[YouTube link to be updated\]](#)

Movie S3.

Evolution of model M2 (no precession cycles). Legend as in Figs. 1 and 2.
Available at [\[YouTube link to be updated\]](#)